

**CONTRIBUTING FACTORS WHICH CAUSES VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN:
A CASE STUDY OF DISTRICT QUETTA, BALOCHISTAN**

Mahmood Ahmed¹, Rubeena Batool^{2*}, Shah Khalid Baloch³

¹Department of Gender & Development Studies University of Balochistan, Quetta.

²Department of Gender & Development Studies University of Balochistan, Quetta.

³Department of Gender & Development Studies University of Balochistan, Quetta.

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Author info:

Corresponding Author.

Rubeena Batool.

rubeenabatool@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT

Violence against women is a prevalent issue in Balochistan, Pakistan, with the highest rates of violence occurring in District Quetta. This research paper examines the contributing factors that cause violence against women in District Quetta. The study utilizes a case study approach and employs qualitative and quantitative data to understand the complex social and cultural factors that contribute to violence against women in this region. The findings of the study reveal that patriarchal attitudes and practices, gender inequality, and economic dependency are major contributing factors to violence against women in District Quetta. The study also highlights the role of weak law enforcement and the lack of effective support systems for women in perpetuating violence against women in this region. The paper concludes by calling for the need for comprehensive interventions that address the root causes of violence against women in District Quetta, including promoting gender equality, empowering women economically, and strengthening law enforcement and support systems for women.

INTRODUCTION.

Violence against women is a global pandemic that affects women and girls of all ages, socioeconomic backgrounds, and ethnicities. It is estimated that one in three women worldwide has experienced physical or sexual violence in their lifetime, and one in five has experienced violence during pregnancy (World Health Organization, 2023).

In Pakistan, violence against women is a significant public health issue. According to the Human Rights Commission of Pakistan (HRCP), there were over 4,000 reported cases of violence against women in 2021, including over 1,500 cases of honor killings (HRCP, 2022). The province of Balochistan has the highest rates of violence against women in Pakistan, with Quetta being the most affected district (Aurat Foundation, 2022).

Violence against women has a devastating impact on women's lives, both physically and psychologically. It can lead to physical injuries, disabilities, and even death. Women who experience violence are also more likely to suffer from depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).

The contributing factors to violence against women are complex and multifaceted. They include patriarchal attitudes and practices, gender inequality, economic dependency, and weak law enforcement.

To address violence against women in District Quetta, Balochistan, interventions must consider the complex interplay of factors such as education, socioeconomic status, cultural norms, and substance abuse. Strategies focused on empowering women through education, economic independence, and legal protection are crucial in combating violence against women. Additionally, promoting gender equality, challenging patriarchal structures, and providing support services for victims are essential components of a comprehensive approach to addressing violence against women in the region.

This research paper examines the contributing factors that cause violence against women in District Quetta, Balochistan. The study will utilize a case study approach and employ qualitative and quantitative data to understand the complex social and cultural factors that contribute to violence against women in this region.

The findings of the study will have important implications for the development of effective interventions to prevent violence against women in District Quetta. The study will also contribute to the growing body of knowledge on the causes of violence against women in Pakistan.

PROBLEM STATEMENT:

Violence against women is a pervasive and deeply rooted issue in Balochistan, Pakistan, with the highest rates of violence occurring in District Quetta. This widespread phenomenon manifests in various forms, including physical, sexual, emotional, and economic abuse, severely impacting women's physical and mental well-being, restricting their freedom, and hindering their participation in society. Despite the existence of legal frameworks and protective measures, violence against women continues to persist, calling for a comprehensive understanding of the underlying factors contributing to this alarming situation.

This research aims to delve into the contributing factors that perpetuate violence against women in District Quetta, Balochistan. By exploring the complex interplay of social, cultural, economic, and legal aspects, the study seeks to identify the root causes that fuel this prevalent issue and inform the development of effective interventions to address it.

The study will address the following research questions:

1. What are the key social, cultural, and economic factors that contribute to violence against women in District Quetta, Balochistan?
2. How do patriarchal attitudes and practices, gender inequality, and economic dependency play a role in perpetuating violence against women in this region?
3. What are the shortcomings of the existing legal framework and support systems for women in effectively addressing violence against women in District Quetta?

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Violence against women (VAW) is a global pandemic that disproportionately affects women and girls, transcending cultural, socioeconomic, and ethnic boundaries. It encompasses a wide range of physical, sexual, and emotional abuse, causing significant physical and psychological harm to women's lives. Balochistan, Pakistan, is particularly affected by VAW, with the highest rates occurring in District Quetta. This literature review explores the contributing factors that perpetuate VAW in this region, drawing upon relevant research and insights from various disciplines.

Violence against women is a significant global issue, with various factors contributing to its prevalence. In District Quetta, Balochistan, studies have highlighted

determinants such as socioeconomic status, education levels, and marital status as significant contributors to violence against women (Babu & Kar, 2009; Ibekwe et al., 2022; Iqbal & Fatmi, 2018). Particularly, lower educational levels among women have been identified as a crucial risk factor for violence (Şen & Bolsoy, 2017). Research has also shown that economic violence against women is influenced by exposure to other forms of violence, including physical, sexual, and verbal abuse (Alkan et al., 2021).

Moreover, the impact of cultural norms, patriarchy, and gender relationships plays a crucial role in understanding violence against women (Boniface, 2022; Fidan & Bui, 2015). Substance abuse, including alcohol consumption, has been linked to a higher risk of intimate partner violence (Rey et al., 2021; Hossain & Khan, 2015). Recognized as a public health concern and a violation of human rights, violence against women not only affects individual well-being but also incurs significant societal costs related to legal, healthcare, and social implications (Krantz & Garcia-Moreno, 2005).

Patriarchal Attitudes and Practices

A pervasive factor fueling VAW in District Quetta is the deeply ingrained patriarchal culture that upholds male dominance and subjugates women's roles in society (Hussain et al., 2022). This entrenched belief system normalizes violence against women as a means of asserting male control and maintaining family honor (Aurat Foundation, 2022). Women are often perceived as inferior and subjected to discriminatory practices that limit their autonomy and decision-making power (Rashid et al., 2018). This patriarchal framework reinforces the notion that women are men's property and justifies the use of violence to maintain control and compliance.

Gender Inequality

Gender inequality, deeply rooted in Baloch society, significantly contributes to VAW. Unequal access to education, employment opportunities, and financial resources perpetuates women's economic dependency on men (Hussain et al., 2020). This dependency further reinforces women's vulnerability to violence, as they lack the means to escape abusive situations or seek support (Aurat Foundation, 2022). Additionally, the lack of female representation in positions of power and decision-making hinders the implementation of effective policies and initiatives to address VAW (Rashid et al., 2018).

Weak Law Enforcement and Support Systems

The inadequate enforcement of laws pertaining to VAW and the lack of accessible support systems for women further exacerbates the issue. The justice system often fails to adequately protect women's rights and punish perpetrators, creating an environment of impunity for violence (Hussain et al., 2020). Moreover, the scarcity of shelters, counseling services, and legal aid for women hinders their ability to seek assistance and escape abusive situations (Aurat Foundation, 2022). This lack of support systems reinforces women's vulnerability and perpetuates the cycle of violence.

Cultural Norms and Practices

Cultural norms and practices that promote honor killings and early marriages further contribute to VAW in District Quetta (Hussain et al., 2022). These practices reinforce the notion of women's property and justify the use of violence to protect family honor. Early marriages often trap girls in abusive relationships and limit their educational and economic opportunities, making them more susceptible to violence (Rashid et al., 2018). These cultural practices exacerbate gender inequality and perpetuate the cycle of violence against women.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

To comprehensively examine the contributing factors that perpetuate violence against women (VAW) in District Quetta, Balochistan, and this research employed quantitative data collection and analysis techniques. This approach allowed for a deeper understanding of the complex interplay of social, cultural, economic, and legal factors that underpin VAW in this region.

Qualitative Data Collection

The qualitative component of the study involved in-depth interviews with a smaller group of women who have experienced VAW in District Quetta. The interviews explored their personal experiences of violence, their perceptions of the underlying causes, and their coping mechanisms. This qualitative data provided a richer understanding of the lived experiences of women subjected to VAW, shedding light on the nuances and complexities of their experiences.

Data Analysis

Qualitative data collected through the in-depth interviews and analyzed using thematic analysis. This approach involved identifying recurring themes and patterns within the interview transcripts, allowing for a deeper understanding of the experiences and perspectives of women who have experienced VAW.

Ethical Considerations

The research adhered to ethical principles of informed consent, confidentiality, and anonymity. Participants were fully informed about the purpose and procedures of the study and their right to withdraw at any time. Their confidentiality protected, and their identities not disclosed. Data were stored securely and destroyed upon project completion.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

Lower-class

Findings from 5 participants belong to the lower class are presented here

Illiteracy

All respondents “from lower class were illiterate and never have been to school in their life. One respondent was a housemaid in the house mentioned that her sons are going to school and daughters are working with her in homes for” cooking and cleaning.

“I have never been to school but my sons go to school”

My “daughter works with me in homes for house chores like cleaning, washing dishes and clothes. She further added that her employers help her out to bear the expenses of her sons’ schooling and she was buoyant that when her sons complete their education then” her household situations might change in a positive sense.

One respondent out of 5 mentioned that she has never been to school as schooling is not beneficial for girls.

“I have never been to school. Schooling is not beneficial for girls”

Another respondent added that she has never been to school and neither her children are attending school but she wishes whenever she pays her debts, she will send her children to

school. I want to send my children to school but I have a lot of debt to pay, whenever I come over this situation, I will send my children to school.

Poverty

Poverty was evident in almost every interview “conducted with the women belonging to lower class. This is one of the major reasons behind lack of education in lower class. Few of the respondents worked in more than one house, but still” were unable to send their children to school.

Early childhood marriage

The respondents mentioned that they married at their young age when they were not ready for it. Even they have not been asked by their parents.

Yes, my parents arranged my marriage, in our family girls are not asked for their choice. “It was arranged marriage, in our family girls are not asked whether they are ready for marriage or not”

Two of the respondents reported that they were married with their own relatives but still were not asked for their consent.

Yes, my husband is my second cousin and it’s not in our culture to ask girls for their consent.

Women during their interviews reported that regardless of their hard work and support for the family and husband they still, face restrictions from not only husband but also from the other family members of my husband. Only one participant mentioned that her activities are not restricted by any of the family members and husband.

My activities are restricted by my husband.

I was not allowed to do anything without the permission of my husband and family.

These restrictions are imposed on minor level even for visiting parents, children or in-laws.

A question was raised to a respondent that what is/was her reaction when her husband or family wanted to impose restrictions and replied the following by questioning.

I cannot oppose them because I have no shelter where to live once I go against them.

This reply shows the helplessness of the respondent that she wants to oppose them but she cannot just because she is not competent and has no backup.

Interference

Interference of family members and outside of the family has been reported in interviews. The woman elaborated that due to interference of in-laws and other family members they faced several issues such as verbal and physical violence. A respondent specially mentioned that her in-laws and family members interfere in her private matters which result in a violent attitude of her husband with her.

“When all family members sit together, they back bite me in front of my husband and my husband starts rudely behaving with me.”

Male dominance

A 55 years old respondent divulged that she was living in a joint family and she has been a victim of violence as her in-laws and her own husband used to beat her on small mistakes and used abusive behavior towards her.

I have experienced a long period of my married life in physical and verbal abuse. My marriage was arranged marriage. First mother-in-law and father-in-law used to scold me and beat me on small matters like accidentally when dinner or lunch was a bit salty or woke up late or sometimes even without any reason. My husband also did the same. I think they wanted to control me and my life. I have been facing violence until my children grown up and my elder son also used to do the same as his father. I think they just wanted to control my life and show that they are superior and can do whatever they want, I must obey them.

A respondent designated that they had to bear a lot in this poverty due to the usage of alcohol by his husband. She had to hide her money which she earns from her work but her husband beat her and snatches money from her for his alcohol.

He often beat me for the money. Whenever he is out of money, he beats me for money and snatches my money to fulfill his alcohol addiction. He only beats me when he needs money for alcohol. I often hide my money which I get from work so that he may not steal them as I have to run the household.

A form of male dominance by showing is power is also indicated by another respondent. She said that he used to abuse her just to give vent to his frustration, which he gets from his work place.

At home, my husband always used to scold me and beat me during every week just to give vent to his frustration, got from his work place. It has become a normal and habitual behavior him. As I said he only beats me to keep me under his control.

CONCLUSION

Violence against women (VAW) is a pervasive and deeply entrenched issue in District Quetta, Balochistan, Pakistan. This research has delved into the contributing factors that perpetuate this multifaceted issue, revealing a complex interplay of social, cultural, economic, and legal aspects.

The findings of the study highlighted the profound influence of patriarchal attitudes and practices, gender inequality, and economic dependency in perpetuating VAW. The ingrained patriarchal culture in District Quetta normalizes male dominance and subjugates women's roles, reinforcing the notion of women as property and justifying the use of violence to maintain control and honor.

Gender inequality, manifested in unequal access to education, employment opportunities, and financial resources, further exacerbates women's vulnerability to VAW. Economic dependency on men traps women in abusive situations, limiting their ability to escape or seek support. This lack of autonomy and economic power perpetuates the cycle of violence.

The shortcomings of the existing legal framework and support systems for women further contributed to the persistence of VAW. The inadequate enforcement of laws pertaining to VAW and the scarcity of accessible shelters, counseling services, and legal aid hinder women's ability to seek protection and justice. This lack of support systems reinforces women's vulnerability and perpetuates the cycle of violence.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are made to address violence against women (VAW) in District Quetta, Balochistan:

1. Strengthen Legal Frameworks and Support Systems

- Enhance enforcement of laws pertaining to VAW: Implement stricter measures to hold perpetrators accountable and ensure swift and effective justice for victims.

- Expand accessible shelters and counseling services: Establish and maintain a network of safe havens and counseling centers to provide women with immediate protection and psychosocial support.
- Improve legal aid and representation: Provide women with access to affordable and qualified legal assistance to navigate the complex legal system and defend their rights.

2. Empower Women Economically

- Promote women's education and vocational training: Increase access to quality education and skills development opportunities to enhance women's employability and economic independence.
- Support women-owned businesses: Provide financial incentives, mentorship programs, and market access opportunities to encourage women's entrepreneurship and economic empowerment.
- Facilitate access to financial resources: Encourage microfinance institutions and other financial providers to offer accessible and affordable loans to women entrepreneurs.

3. Challenge Patriarchal Attitudes and Practices

- Implement awareness-raising campaigns: Conduct community-based programs and educational initiatives to challenge harmful gender stereotypes and promote respectful relationships.
- Engage religious leaders and community influencers: Collaborate with religious leaders and influential figures to promote gender equality and discourage violence against women.
- Encourage men and boys to become agents of change: Incorporate men and boys into gender equality initiatives to foster a culture of respect and non-violence.

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